

THE ATTENTION TO EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13854008>

ANNOTATION

This article briefly outlines one of the key directions of New Uzbekistan's development strategy for 2022–2026, as outlined in the state program aimed at implementing this strategy. The focus of this strategy is to further enhance the development of human capital through a just social policy. It emphasizes improving the quality of education at all levels within our country's education system, directing the younger generation toward vocational and professional development, and achieving the primary goal of preparing highly competent professionals.

Key terms: Human capital, just social policy, improvement of the education system, development strategy, state program, vocational education, national curriculum, non-state education

INTRODUCTION

Today, our nation is experiencing significant changes. In particular, the adoption of the "New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026," which is based on seven priority directions and developed following broad public discussions under the initiative of our President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, within the framework of the principle "From the Action Strategy to the Development Strategy" has marked the beginning of a new era of deep democratic reforms and transformational changes in our country. The work carried out within the framework of the Action Strategy encompassed all sectors. Most importantly, the main goal of the reforms was set as improving the quality of education in our country, ensuring human rights and freedoms, dignity, and interests, as well as the accountability of state bodies to society. The Development Strategy, undoubtedly, will be a logical and continuous continuation of these efforts.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The works and speeches of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as relevant literature and internet sources were used. During the writing of the article, theoretical-deductive conclusions, analysis and synthesis, and the principles of logical reasoning were employed.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

As is well known, the content and significance of the speech delivered by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the joint session of the chambers of the Supreme Assembly dedicated to his inauguration were warmly welcomed by students, public servants, scholars, experts, and the broader community.

It is important to highlight that the President's speech was future-oriented and served as a practical program for the country's development strategy. In his speech at the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated: "Every time I meet with our youth, I draw strength and energy from your enthusiasm and determination, which lifts my spirits. I know that each of you is burning with the desire to serve our beloved homeland and people wholeheartedly. I highly value you as the greatest wealth and priceless treasure of Uzbekistan. In any reforms we undertake in our country, we rely first and foremost on youth like you, on your strength, determination, and spirit. As you all know, we have set immense goals for ourselves today. We have embarked on creating the foundation for the Third Renaissance in our Motherland. We consider family, preschool education, schools, and higher education, as well as cultural and scientific institutions, to be the most important links in this future Renaissance. Therefore, we are systematically implementing deep reforms in these areas. I believe that dedicated and patriotic youth like you will actively participate in creating a new foundation for our country's development and make a significant contribution."

The head of state, in his address, comprehensively covered all aspects of the country's life, proposing new ideas, innovations, and initiatives. The President of Uzbekistan outlined seven priority areas of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy in his speech. This conceptual document establishes the principle of "From the Strategy of Actions to the Strategy of Development" as the main idea and guiding criterion to ensure the continuity and sustainability of reforms.

"Taking into account the demands of our people, we have developed the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy and subjected it to a unique nationwide discussion during the electoral process. In this important conceptual document, the principle of 'From the Strategy of Actions to the Strategy of Development' has been placed on the agenda to ensure the continuity and sustainability of our reforms," the president stated.

Notably, the issue of quality education and upbringing has been emphasized as a constant focus. To this end, plans are in place to consistently increase teachers' monthly salaries, aiming to reach \$1,000 by 2025. A National Education Program has been developed to construct new schools, strengthen the

material and technical base of existing institutions, and ensure continuity across all levels of education.

It is important to acknowledge that in the past five years, several systematic reforms have been implemented in the social sector, yielding positive results. However, there are still several problems and shortcomings that hinder the establishment of effective mechanisms in this area. The development strategy places special importance on social reforms.

As noted, this development strategy consists of seven areas. The fourth area focuses on implementing a fair social policy aimed at developing human capital, which has become a priority for the reforms being carried out in our country. Additionally, the following goals and tasks have been established for this area:

- Implement a system to support high school graduates who wish to learn a profession, ensuring that at least one profession is acquired through state assistance.

- Increase the coverage of 6-year-old children in the preschool preparation system to 90% by the 2022/2023 academic year and to 100% by the end of the 2024/2025 academic year.

- Establish over 7,000 new non-state preschool educational organizations by attracting private sector funding into the preschool education system.

- Improve the qualifications of over 160,000 pedagogical staff between 2022 and 2026.

- Develop and implement a national program aimed at building new schools, increasing private schools, and improving the quality of education.

- Increase the number of educational places to 6.4 million by the end of 2026.

- Implement a program for the development of 217 "Barkamol Avlod" children's schools from 2022 to 2026.

- Establish more than 100,000 free clubs equipped with the necessary resources to introduce youth to the world of art and to provide knowledge and skills in computer and IT technologies.

- Establish transport connections to schools and preschool educational institutions in remote areas.

- Create new textbooks, exercise books, teacher methodology books, and mobile applications based on the national curriculum, totaling 699 titles by 2026, including 296 titles in 2022.

- Create a total of 769 video lessons for the Electronic Qualification Improvement Platform to train teachers in new methodologies based on the national curriculum by 2026.

- Implement a system for testing and expert evaluation of textbooks and educational-methodical sets in general education schools with the participation of foreign specialists.

- Gradually increase the salaries of talented teachers based on qualification categories.

- Completely review the procedure for granting qualification categories to teachers and establish a fair and transparent system based on competency assessment methodologies.

- Set certification requirements for local or international standards for each subject taught in schools.

- Diagnose the knowledge and skills of teachers who do not have certification.

- Continue efforts to fill general education schools, especially in remote areas, with highly educated teaching staff.

- Further improve the appointment system for school directors and their deputies, ensuring the involvement of school teachers and parents.

- Optimize the activities of district divisions of the public education system through complete digitization.

- Introduced a system to provide free meals for primary school (grades 1-4) students in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm region as a pilot project.

- Consider the expansion of the free meal system for primary school (grades 1-4) students based on the results of the pilot project.

This direction of tasks will be an integral continuation of the extensive reforms aimed at ensuring human dignity and legal interests over the past five years, elevating them to a new level.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Improving the quality of education effectively and continuously supplying highly qualified personnel is an ongoing process. From this perspective, it can be concluded that the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan outlines important tasks and goals for the next five years regarding the implementation of a fair social policy and the development of human capital. Thus, the process of extensive reforms will continue consistently, and it is in the interest of our entire nation that these reforms be productive. We are all responsible for their

successful implementation. Indeed, our unity and solidarity are crucial for the future and development of our country.

We believe that all state and public organizations, representatives of civil society institutions, and non-governmental non-profit organizations will actively participate in the implementation of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy. The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy will mark a new stage in our national development and will serve as a cohesive spiritual foundation and benchmark that unites our people towards common goals.

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